

A Comparative Study On the Utilization of Calcium by Wad Goats Fed Groundnut Cake, Activated Sewage Sludge and Poultry Waste Based Diets

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Abstract:

A comparative study on the effective utilization of calcium in Groundnut Cake (GNC), Dried Activated Sewage Sludge (DASS) and Poultry Waste (PW) based diets was carried out using Eighteen (18) West African Dwarf (WAD) goats. Calcium in the 3 different diets were highly digestible and therefore well-utilized. Digestibility coefficient (%) of calcium in the three (3) diets are as follows: 36.74, 75.43 and 53.82 respectively. Statistical analysis ($P < 0.05$) showed significant treatment effects for intake, digestibility, and balance of Ca.

Keywords: Comparative, Utilization, Calcium, Groundnut cake, Poultry Waste, Dried Activated Sewage Sludge,

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Introduction

The chronic shortage of conventional oil cakes for livestock feeding in most developing countries has compelled the search for alternatives for these costly protein supplements. Groundnut cake is the conventionally used protein supplement in the ration of ruminants in most parts of the country but at times its limited supply and seasonal availability escalate its cost (Nagalakshmi & Dhanalakshmi, 2015). The use of animal waste to replace groundnut cake in feed formulation would lower cost and livestock production and lead to a significant reduction in the cost of milk, meat, and other livestock products. According to Tadele (2015), animal wastes represent a vast reservoir of cheap nutrients, particularly for ruminants. A lot of work has been done on the ability of indigenous livestock to effectively utilize the protein and energy present in animal wastes however little importance has been given to the utilization of some of the major minerals in animal wastes by indigenous livestock in Nigeria. But as reported by IAEA (1971), the production of the much-needed animal protein can be severely curtailed when unrecognized conditions of deficiency, oversupply or imbalance of minerals exist and interfere with the intensification of livestock production. Poultry wastes as a dietary supplement have been used successfully to feed ruminants (Oltjen & Dinius, 1976) and Poultry (Ologhobo & Oyewole, 1986).

Dried Activated Sewage Sludge is the solids left after the processing of Sewage through a waste treatment plant (Sebastian & Mariusz, 2019; Anna & Aneta, 2019) and has been incorporated in small quantities into the diets of ruminants (Adeleye et al., 1987), poultry (Biobaku et al., 2021), Pigs (Ekpenyong et al., 1989). Sewage sludge has sufficient required nutrients to be attractive for animal feed. Activated sewage sludge and Poultry wastes have been used extensively as feed for various classes of animals however, their mineral contribution to livestock production is yet to be fully explained compared with energy and protein. Therefore, the present study is designed to contribute to the existing knowledge of Groundnut cake, activated sewage sludge and Poultry Wastes as livestock feed by appraising the utilization of calcium in these feeding stuff when fed as a supplement to West African Dwarf Goats.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site and Sample collection

This feeding trial was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Ibadan, Ibadan. The Poultry droppings were collected from the layer unit of the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Ibadan, Ibadan while The Dry Activated Sewage Sludge was obtained from the sewage treatment plant of the University College Hospital (U.C.H.), Ibadan

Experimental Diets

Three different test diets were prepared for this trial. Diet one, the control ration, was made up of a basal diet plus a concentrate ration made up of Groundnut cake (GNC), diet two consisted of a basal diet plus a concentrate ration in which Dried Activated Sewage Sludge (DASS) was used to replace GNC while diet three consisted of a basal diet plus a concentrate ration whereby Poultry Waste (PW) was used to replace GNC as the source of Nitrogen. They

were all isonitrogenous. The per cent composition and the proximate analysis of the experimental diets are shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Percent Composition of Experimental Supplement Ration

Ingredients	Diet one	Diet Two	Diet Three
Cassava flour	49.5	37.0	32.5
Groundnut cake	25	-	-
Dried Activated Sewage Sludge	-	37.5	-
Poultry Waste	-	-	42
Dried brewers' grain	25.0	25.0	25.0
Mineral Mixture	0.25	0.25	0.25
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25

Table 2: Proximate Composition of the Supplemental Rations

	Grass	Supplemental Ration		
		Diet I (%)	Diet II (%)	Diet III (%)
Dry Matter	62.1	94	97	98.3
Crude Protein	6.8	19.3	14.8	18.6
Crude Fiber	51.9	9.5	25.7	18.8
Ether Extract	1.5	2	2.5	3.5
Ash	5.0	6	33.5	8.5
N.F. E	34.9	63.3	23.5	50.6

Experimental Layout and Animal Management

Each diet was replicated six (6) times with one goat per replicate. The goats certified free from helminths and intestinal parasites were kept in individual metabolism cages designed for separate collection of urine and faeces. Each animal was fed daily with 1kg of the basal diet made up of giant Star grass (*Cynodon nlemfuensis*) plus 1kg of concentrate. They had free access to fresh and clean water daily. The feeding period consisted of a preliminary feeding period of 2 weeks followed by a 3-day collection period. The preliminary period was to allow the animal to adjust to the experimental diet. Feeds leftover from the previous day's ration were collected and weighed daily to estimate the feed intake by each animal. Each animal was weighed both at the beginning and the end of the collection period.

Faecal Collection

Faeces of each animal were collected each morning during the 3-day collection period before feeding the animal its ration for the day. The faeces collected daily from each animal during

the collection period were weighed and dried at 70°C in the hot air oven to constant weight. The dried samples were bulked and stored at room temperature until required for chemical analysis.

Analytical Procedure

Dry matter was determined as described by AOAC (1970). One gram of the dried faeces was weighed separately into Kjeldahl flasks for digestion using 20mls of Nitric acid and 4mls perchloric. The percentage of calcium in the digest was determined using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Statistical Analysis

The data from the feeding trial were subjected to an Analysis of variance in compliance with Steel and Torrie (1960).

Results and Discussion

The proximate Analysis for the three diets is shown in Table 2. The dry Matter content of Diet III was highest (98.3%), followed by Diet II (97%) and Diet I (94%). The Crude Protein content of Diet I was highest with a value of 19.3% followed by Diet III (18.6%) and Diet II (14.8%). Diet II had the highest Crude Fibre and Ash content.

Feed Intake and Weight Gains of Animals on the Three Experimental Rations

Table 3 shows the daily dry matter intake per metabolic size of the WAD Goats. The mean intakes for Diets I, II and III were 173.5gms, 87.51gms, and 158.57gms respectively. The low intake of Diet II could be because high levels of inclusion of DASS in a ration cause some reduction in acceptability (Hacker et al, 1957). This also agrees with Adeleye et al., (1987), who observed adverse effects with sheep fed up to 40% of DASS. Statistical analysis showed that treatment effects were highly significant ($P < .01$). On further subjection to Duncan's multiple range test, significant differences were obtained between the means of Diet I and Diet II and between the means of Diet II and Diet III. There was no significant difference observed between the means of Diet I and Diet III.

Table 3: Daily Dry Matter Intake Per Metabolic Size by Goats Fed Gnc, Sewage and Poultry Waste Diets

REPLICATE	I	II	III
1	180.42	173.81	150.97
2	163.56	140.36	163.28
3	185.76	75.44	151.65
4	209.29	43.23	157.4
5	174.83	49.98	157.42
6	127.15	42.23	172.5
N	173.5	87.51	158.57
SD	27.31	56.22	8.05

X = mean.

SD = Standard deviation

Table 4: Summary of Change in Weight of WAD Goats Fed Groundnut cake and Sewage Sludge and Poultry Waste based diet

Diet	Mean Initial Weight(kg)	Mean Final Weight(kg)	Mean Changes in Weight (kg)
I	5.8	6.2	0.38
II	5.6	5.5	-0.06
III	5.9	6.1	0.23

The performance of the goats was quite encouraging. Although goats on GNC-based diets recorded the highest growth rate (6.2kg, Table 3), the apparent differences were not statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). This showed that DASS and PW could successfully replace GNC. The mean growth rates obtained for goats on all treatments were quite meaningful for WAD goats receiving adequate voluntary DM intake (Akinsoyinu & Adelaye, 1987). Digestibility coefficients (Table 5) seem to be quite reasonable for ruminants (Adebowale & Ademosun, 1985).

TABLE 5: Summary of Apparent Digestibility of the Ration

Diet	DM Intake(g/day)	Faecal Output (DM/g/day)	Digestibility coefficient (%)	SD
I (GNC)	664.57	101.52	84.69	4.4
II (DASS)	321.78	51.48	82.22	10
III (PW)	606.06	136.18	78.43	9.6

The mean apparent digestibility coefficients of the three experimental diets are depicted in Table 5. Diet I had an apparent digestibility coefficient of 84.69%, Diet II, 82.22% and Diet III, 78.43%. The results showed that all the diets were highly digestible. Table 5 also shows that animals on diet II consumed little of the feed and excreted also very little of the feed in their faeces. They utilized the little they consumed as can be seen by the high digestibility coefficient. The high digestibility observed for diet II could be due to the fact that most of the Dry matter intake of goats fed diet II was from the grass. Goats according to Davendra (1971) have a high digestive efficiency for cellulose found in poor quality grasses with high crude fibre content. Diet I was highly utilized by the animals. The data shows that animals on diet I had a mean dry matter intake of 664.57gms and a mean faecal output of 101.92gms as compared to Diet III where animals had a mean dry matter intake of 606.06gms and a mean faecal output of 136.18gms. The high intake of diet I could be due to palatability of the ration containing Groundnut cake (GNC) as compared to the rations containing animal wastes. Statistical analysis showed that the digestibility coefficient of the 3 diets were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) different.

Table 6: Summary of Calcium Utilization by WAD Goats Fed GNC, DASS and PW Based Diets

Diet	Calcium Intake (DM/g/day)	Calcium in Faeces (DM/g/day)	Apparent Digestibility Coefficient	Calcium - balance (g/day)	Calcium-balance g/day/kgw ^{0.75}

			(%)		
I	1.18 ^a	0.79 ^a	36.74 ^a	0.39 ^a	0.11 ^a
II	1.06 ^a	0.21 ^a	75.43 ^b	0.85 ^a	0.23 ^a
III	10.47 ^b	4.99 ^b	53.82 ^{ab}	5.48 ^b	1.48 ^b

Diet I = Groundnut cake-based diet Diet II = Sewage sludge-based diet Diet III = Poultry waste-based diet

a,b,c = figures with identical superscripts are not significant (P>0.05)

Statistical analysis showed significant differences (p<0.05) for Calcium intake, fecal output and calcium balance per metabolic size of goats between diet 1 and diet III. There was however no significant difference between diet I and diet II for calcium intake, fecal output and calcium balance per metabolic size of goats. Calcium balance per metabolic size of goats was highest for diet III composed of poultry waste than for diets 1 and 11. This may be explained by the high contents of Ca in the diet. However, the apparent digestibility coefficient for Ca in Diet 3 was lower than that in Diet 2 but higher than that in Diet 1. Statistical analysis showed differences in Ca digestibility between the diets (P<0.05).

The Figures below show the box plot for calcium utilization in WAD goats fed GNC, DASS and PW Based Diets

Correlation Analysis

Tables 7a,b and c show the correlation in utilization of calcium in GNC, PW and DASS

Table 7a: Correlation in Utilization of Calcium

GNC Correlation Matrix in CA	CA.intake	CA.in.faeces	CA.Digestibility.coefficient	Ca.Balance	Ca.balance.day.kgw0.75
CA.intake	1	0.617 (.192)	-0.276 (.596)	-0.087 (.870)	-0.094 (.860)
CA.in.faeces	0.617 (.192)	1	-0.886 (.019)	-0.838 (.037)	-0.841 (.036)
CA.Digestibility.coefficient	-0.276 (.596)	-0.886 (.019)	1	0.930 (.007)	0.936 (.006)

<i>Ca.Balance</i>	-0.087 (.870)	-0.838 (.037)	0.930 (.007)	1	0.999 (<.001)
<i>Ca.balance.day.kgw0.75</i>	-0.094 (.860)	-0.841 (.036)	0.936 (.006)	0.999 (<.001)	1
<i>Computed correlation used pearson-method with listwise-deletion.</i>					

N.B: (0.192) means the significant level... Any value greater than the alpha value (0.05) means there is no significant different in the mean

Table 7b: Correlation in Utilization of Calcium

PW Correlation Matrix in Ca	<i>CA.intake</i>	<i>CA.in.faece s</i>	<i>CA.Digestibilit y.coefficient</i>	<i>Ca.Balanc e</i>	<i>Ca.balance.da y.kgw0.75</i>
<i>CA.intake</i>	1	0.880 (.021)	-0.801 (.055)	-0.638 (.173)	-0.717 (.109)
<i>CA.in.faeces</i>	0.880 (.021)	1	-0.988 (<.001)	-0.927 (.008)	-0.957 (.003)
<i>CA.Digestibility.coeff icient</i>	-0.801 (.055)	-0.988 (<.001)	1	0.970 (.001)	0.988 (<.001)
<i>Ca.Balance</i>	-0.638 (.173)	-0.927 (.008)	0.970 (.001)	1	0.987 (<.001)
<i>Ca.balance.day.kgw 0.75</i>	-0.717 (.109)	-0.957 (.003)	0.988 (<.001)	0.987 (<.001)	1
<i>Computed correlation used pearson-method with listwise-deletion.</i>					

DASS Correlation Matrix in Ca	<i>CA.intak e</i>	<i>CA.in.faec es</i>	<i>CA.Digestibilit y.coefficient</i>	<i>Ca.Balanc e</i>	<i>Ca.balanc e.day.kgw</i>
<i>CA.intake</i>	1	0.865 (.026)	0.500 (.312)	0.995 (<.001)	0.959 (.003)
<i>CA.in.faeces</i>	0.865 (.026)	1	0.040 (.941)	0.814 (.049)	0.697 (.124)

CA.Digestibility.coefficient	0.500 (.312)	0.040 (.941)	1	0.573 (.235)	0.649 (.163)
Ca.Balance	0.995 (<.001)	0.814 (.049)	0.573 (.235)	1	0.979 (.001)
Ca.balance.day.kgw0.75	0.959 (.003)	0.697 (.124)	0.649 (.163)	0.979 (.001)	1
<i>Computed correlation used pearson-method with listwise-deletion.</i>					

Table 7c: Correlation in Utilization of Calcium**Conclusion**

This study concluded that the differences observed were not significant. Values of calcium digestibility suggested that DASS and PW could successfully replace the conventional groundnut cake as sources of calcium in goat diets.

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